

D7.3 Data Management Plan

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Flex4Res members of consortium

Table 1: Consortium members

Partner name	Shortcode	Website link
PANEPISTIMIO PATRON	LMS	https://lms.mech.upatras.gr/
VOESTALPINE HIGH PERFORMANCE METALS DIGITAL SOLUTIONS GMBH	VOE	https://www.voestalpine.com/group/en/
SIDENOR VIOMICHANIKI CHALYVA ANONYMI ETAIRIA	SID	https://sidenor.gr/en/
HANS BERG GMBH&CO KG	HANS	https://www.berg-kg.de/de/
GOIMEK S COOP	GOI	https://www.goimek.com/es
SORALUCE S. COOP.	SOR	https://www.soraluce.com/en
EIT MANUFACTURING CENTRAL GGMBH	EITM	https://www.eitmanufacturing.eu/
NETCOMPANY-INTRASOFT SA	INTRA	https://www.netcompany-intrasoft.com/
CONTACT SOFTWARE GMBH	CONT	https://contact-software.com/
A1 DIGITAL INTERNATIONAL GMBH	A1	https://www.a1.digital/
BEIA	BEIA	https://beia.be/
SAVVY DATA SYSTEMS SL	SAV	https://www.savvydatasystems.com/es/inicio
MONDRAGON CORPORACION COOPERATIVA SCOOP	MON	https://www.mondragon-corporation.com/
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET WIEN	TU Wien	http://www.ift.at/
TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT DARMSTADT	TUDa	https://www.ptw.tu-darmstadt.de/
UNIVERSITAET SIEGEN	USI	https://www.uni-siegen.de/start/
IDEKO S COOP	IDE	https://www.ideko.es/

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List of Abbreviations

Table 2: List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
AAS	Asset Administration Shell
AI	Artificial Intelligence
API	Application Programming Interface
CBR	Case Based Reasoning
CNC	Computerized Numerical Control
DRS	Delay Recording System
EAF	Electric Arc Furnace
EC	European Commission
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
EU	European Union
FO	Fabrication Order
GA	Grant agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HaDEA	European Health and Digital Executive Agency
HMI	Human Machine Interface
HQ	Headquarters
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
IDS	International Data Spaces
IF	Induction Furnace
IMU	Inertial Measurement Unit
IoT	Internet of Things
O&M	Operation and Maintenance
PAC	Programmable Automation Controller
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
TBD	To be Determined
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
DMP	Data Management Plan
WP	Work package
FAIR	Findable, Accesible, Interoperable and Re-usable
B2B	Business-to-business
WPL	Work package leader

Executive summary

Flex4Res aims to create an open platform for resilient manufacturing value chains through trusted data sharing. The project is based on Gaia-X and IDS technologies and utilizes the Digital Twin concept to enable reconfiguration processes in flexible production systems and networks.

This deliverable describes the methodology for Data Management Plan (DMP) that will be applied to Flex4Res project. This is the first deliverable (D7.3) of Work Package 7 (WP7) for the Flex4Res project. The methodology that is described aims to protect the data collected or/and generated during the project's activities and make them FAIR as well. The D7.3 is delivered in M06 of the Flex4Res project, and is updated based on the latest information available up to the month of delivery.

The deliverable is organized in five sections:

- ❖ Section 1 provides an introduction, describing the motivation, objectives and delivery requirements.
- ❖ Section 2 is about the data summary to be collected or/and generated during the Flex4Res project, it is also discussed the origin, expected volume and stakeholders.
- ❖ Section 3 documents the FAIR data, where the findable (meta) data, making data openly accessible, data interoperability and mechanisms to increase re
- ❖ use subsections are discussed in details.
- ❖ Section 4 is about the allocation of resources, where estimates the resource requires for making the project's data FAIR
- ❖ Section 5 presents the conclusion of the deliverable and the next steps of the project with respect to the data management plan.
- ❖ The appendix of the document contains the privacy policy of the project portal.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

D7.3 is the first deliverable of WP7 of the Flex4Res project. The project provides an open platform to support production networks' reconfiguration for resilient manufacturing value chains. It is based on efficient ways for trusted data sharing among stakeholders without interoperability barriers. Flex4Res builds on the state-of-the-art Gaia-X and IDS technologies for data sharing in the horizontal supply chain and the Asset Administration Shell (AAS) to implement intra-factory reconfiguration practices. The project considers the Digital Twin of the value-adding network a key enabling technology to achieve reconfiguration processes in highly flexible production systems and networks.

1.2 Objectives

This deliverable aims to provide a Data Management Plan of the collected and generated data that will be used during the project while also making the data FAIR. D7.3 identifies all the anticipated activities to make data FAIR. D7.3 aims to achieve the following objectives:

- Describe the data management plan for collected or/and generated data during the Flex4Res project
- Outline the methodology to protect the collected or/and generated data and make them Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR)
- Collected or/and generated data are discussed and further information is provided
- Describe the ways of making data accessible and searchable to interested stakeholders.
- Present an estimation of the resources allocated to make data FAIR.

1.3 Deliverable requirements

The requirements of the DMP is to discuss and provide further information regarding the objectives that were mentioned in the above subsection. Due to the fact that the DMP is a living document (size of data, changes in the consortium privacy policy etc.), updates that will be made during the project will be documented in the Periodic Reports of the Flex4Res project.

2 Data Summary

In accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), Flex4Res will generate and/or collect meaningful non-sensitive data that does not fall into any special categories of personal data. This data will be analyzed from a variety of methodological perspectives to produce insights that will successfully feed Flex4Res's activities, allow the project partners to deliver results that are supported by evidence, and ultimately help the project achieve its goals. This data may be quantitative, qualitative, or a combination of those in nature. In light of this, the second chapter of the Data Management Plan (DMP) begins by describing the rationale behind the data's collection and generation and how Flex4Res fits into it. It then goes on to describe the various types and formats of this data as well as its history and anticipated volume before coming to a conclusion with a list of potential users.

2.1 Data collection/generation and its relation to the project

Flex4Res involves a number of activities during which data will be collected or generated in order to successfully meet its goals and ensure the production of results that are supported by evidence. The

goal of the activity during which this data is produced and the purpose for which it is collected/generated are related to one another.

In particular, these activities, along with their objectives in the framework of Flex4Res are as follows:

- ❖ Evaluation of stakeholder and potential user needs and requirements to support demand-driven design and development of Flex4Res' pilots.
- ❖ Analyzing the suggestions and comments made during the Flex4Res workshops in order to inform the co-design of the Flex4Res pilots and to develop recommendations on how they might be put into practice and tailored to meet the needs of users and stakeholders.
- ❖ Monitoring, co-evaluation, and validation of Flex4Res' pilots in order to enhance and fine-tune their design and offers based on information and feedback gathered from users of the stakeholders taking part in the project's pilot activities.
- ❖ Improving and validating the business models while taking into account the requirements of prospective users and customers as well as the objectives and goals of the consortium partners of Flex4Res.
- ❖ Monitoring and assessing the outcomes of the project's stakeholder engagement activities in order to efficiently gauge and communicate the progress of these efforts in creating a thriving community.
- ❖ Monitoring and evaluating the project's dissemination and communication results to determine the impact of its pertinent activities, adjusting Flex4Res' strategy accordingly, and meeting the Commission's reporting requirements.

2.2 Types and formats of collected/generated data

Data of a variety of types will be gathered/produced during Flex4Res activities. Depending on the source and physical format, there are numerous ways to categorize the different types of this data¹. However, data is frequently viewed in terms of how it is generated or captured. Electronic text documents, spreadsheets, questionnaires, and transcripts are a few examples. The format in which various data types (qualitative, quantitative, etc.) are stored is another way to think about data. Along these lines, Flex4Res 's data will be available in easily accessible formats, such as post scripts (e.g. pdf, xps, etc.), machine readable formats (xml, html, etc.), spreadsheets (e.g. xls, csv, etc.), text documents (e.g. .docx, rtf, etc.), compressed formats (e.g. rar, zip, etc.) or any other format required by the objectives and methodology of the activity within the frame of which it is produced.

To improve the interoperability and reuse of Flex4Res's data, special attention will be paid to using open formats (such as csv, pdf, zip, etc.) and/or machine-readable formats (such as xml, json, rdf, HTML, etc.). By doing this, we will make the data available in a format that is simple to read and freely usable by anyone with access to the software program.

In considering this, it is possible to categorize the types of data and their formats that are gathered or generated within the Flex4Res framework into three different groups: (i) data gathered or generated through direct input methods; (ii) users of the market; and (iii) data gathered or generated through

¹ Jakobsson, U., Braukmann, R., Lundgren M., Expert Tour Guide on Data Management. Retrieved from <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/1.-Plan>

²According to the Open Data Handbook: "An open format is a file format with no restrictions, monetary or otherwise, placed upon its use and can be fully processed with at least one free/open-source software tool and it is not encumbered by any copyrights, patents, trademarks or other restrictions so that anyone may use it".

³According to the Open Data Handbook: "Machine readable formats are file formats that can be automatically read and processed by a computer. Machine-readable data must be structured data".

dissemination, communication, and stakeholder engagement activities, as further described in the following subsections.

2.2.1 Data collected/generated through direct input methods

Direct input methods in the Flex4Res framework include techniques for gathering data through interactions between consortium partners and outside stakeholders, with the latter supplying the former with data. In a similar vein, outside parties play the part of a data subject, a real person whose personal information is being processed. In particular, the identification and choice of appropriate data subjects are based on purposeful sampling, where consortium partners choose external stakeholders based on their function in the targeted ecosystem and the goals of the specific activity for which data is being collected.

During the Flex4Res project, both quantitative and qualitative data will be gathered and produced:

- ❖ **Quantitative data** is numerical and is gathered through measurement or counting. Quantitative data examples include a company's annual revenue, a worker's hourly wage, the number of SMEs in Europe, etc. These data are amenable to statistical manipulation and can be represented by ordinal, interval, or ratio scales.
- ❖ **Qualitative data**, can be categorized according to physical characteristics, gender, colors, or anything else without a numerical value is known as qualitative data, also known as categorical data. Qualitative data sources also include books, interviews, and various kinds of on-the-ground observation. Qualitative data examples include learning preferences, skill sets, country of origin, etc.

The subsections below provide more information about the various types and formats of data that will be gathered through direct input methods within the framework of Flex4Res.

2.2.1.1 Market gaps and opportunities

This information was gathered to aid in the analysis of the market's needs and the creation of its design. A desk review of secondary data sources in the public domain was part of the work. The data gathered are primarily qualitative and documented as interview transcripts. They provide details on the value propositions, target markets, service offerings (both online and offline), and business models.

2.2.1.2 Pilot monitoring, co-evaluation and validation data

As part of a framework for ongoing monitoring, users and stakeholders who participate in Flex4Res' pilot activities and its pilot cases will be asked for feedback. That will also be implemented to keep track of, evaluate collectively, and validate their performance, ultimately encouraging demand-driven improvement. Survey-based questionnaires will be used to collect quantitative and qualitative information from pilot participants in order to track customer experience metrics and KPIs in order to accomplish this. The components and services participating in the pilot cases will also provide specific data related to the scenarios of the pilot case.

2.2.2 Data collected/generated from dissemination, communication and stakeholder engagement activities

2.2.2.1 Social media statistics (including Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube)

To measure and evaluate the performance and outcomes of the project's social media activity in terms of dissemination and communication, this data will be gathered/generated through routine monitoring of the project's social media statistics (including Twitter, LinkedIn, and YouTube). As a result, the data will be qualitative as well as quantitative in nature and will address the metrics attained on each channel (for example, followers, tweet impressions on twitter, etc.). The results of this step will also be analyzed, along with any potential improvements, in order to meet the project's objectives. Overall, the

information will be kept in a Microsoft Excel file (.xlsx), while the analysis of the outcomes will be kept in a regular Word document (.docx).

2.2.2.2 Data collected from project events (stakeholder engagement events, etc.)

This data will be collected in 2 ways during the implementation of the project, that is:

- ❖ The stakeholder engagement activities planned by Flex4Res, which include participant lists with demographic data on the participants;
- ❖ The participation of Flex4Res consortium partners in pertinent events hosted by third parties in order to connect with and involve stakeholders, as well as general details about the events attended and their outreach

In a similar vein, this data will be gathered to monitor the outcomes of stakeholder engagement activities and give project partners the chance to report on these activities. Additionally, this information will be updated each time a partner participates in or plans an event. The information will be stored in a common spreadsheet (.xlsx) and will be both quantitative and qualitative in nature. subscriptions to newsletters (such as subscriber contact information). Any interested stakeholder may freely provide his or her contact information in a dedicated sign-up form hosted in the project's web portal to receive the most recent news and outcomes of the project, which will aid in the collection of this data. A newsletter will be distributed to subscribers once every three months, and a condensed version will be sent out via email every month. In light of this, this information will be gathered in order to inform any interested parties of the Flex4Res project.

Accordingly, the data will include a list of stakeholders along with their contact details. The information that was gathered in this case included (i) email addresses, (ii) first and last names, (iii) countries, (iv) organization types, (v) regions, and (vi) gender. The parties in charge of gathering and storing this data will draft the necessary consent to explain to potential stakeholders how their data will be stored and that GDPR procedures will be adhered to.

2.2.2.3 Data from dissemination and communication

This information will be gathered by routinely keeping track of the project's various dissemination activities, such as articles published in pertinent journals and blog posts, etc. A list of articles and blog posts written by consortium partners will make up the data. This information is being gathered in order to evaluate the reach and effectiveness of the project's dissemination efforts. All partners have been given access to a template for this purpose, which they can use to suggest activities to be completed and record the activities they actually complete. In order to allow the partners to directly update their input, the template is also made available online. A single Excel file (.xlsx) will be created at the end with all the data combined.

2.3 Origin of data and re-use of pre-existing data

New data will be gathered/generated in the Flex4Res context by consortium partners and outside stakeholders taking part in project activities and/or during the pilot case execution. In light of this, external stakeholder groups from which new data will come, aside from consortium partners, include:

- ❖ Providers of information, knowledge, and innovation (such as those found in academic institutions and their technology/knowledge transfer offices, non-university public research organizations, research and technology organizations, high-tech SMEs and large enterprises, etc.).
- ❖ Those responsible for developing and implementing policy at the regional, national, and EU levels (such as those working for development organizations).

Additionally, specific pre-existing data may also be used in the context of the project. Project partners may provide specific data models, such as existing ontologies, for the pilot executions. Because of these

pre-existing datasets, the Flex4Res project's pilot cases will be executed in an environment that is already populated with interesting content.

2.4 Expected size of data

In order to facilitate the demand-driven, evidence-based development, piloting, evaluation, validation, and fine-tuning of its value propositions, Flex4Res involves a number of activities.

2.5 Data utility

The following table provides a succinct summary of the stakeholders who might find the data that will be collected or generated by the project to be useful (both inside and outside of Flex4Res's consortium), as well as the advantages that might result for them from using this data.

Table 3. Data Utility

Stakeholder Group	Data Utility
Researchers/projects in the resilience manufacturing	Researchers who are interested are welcome to use the Flex4Res data as a starting point for similar problems with resilience assessment and reconfiguration strategies. Additionally, create and conduct new studies that will produce comparable research findings to advance the field and provide ample insight into the evaluation of previous research and the creation of reconfiguration strategies.
Project partners	In order to produce results that are supported by evidence and ultimately accomplish the project's goals, the data gathered or generated during Flex4Res is of utmost importance to project partners. Therefore, this information will make it possible for the project's pilots to be co-designed, developed, validated, and fine-tuned. Additionally, the piloted solutions will be designed, enhanced, and validated using the data. The information may also be useful to project partners after the project has ended, allowing them to develop and seize any interesting concepts or chances that may present themselves in order to fully utilize and maximize the outcomes generated by Flex4Res.

3 FAIR Data

The Commission's Guidelines on Data Management in Horizon 2020 place a strong emphasis on the necessity of making project-generated data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reuseable (FAIR) in order to ensure good data management. This entails using standards and metadata to make data discoverable, defining data sharing policies and which data will be open, enabling data exchange via open repositories, and making the data more reusable. In light of this, the DMP's subsequent sections outline the methodology used in the framework to make data discoverable, accessible, and interoperable as well as to ensure their preservation and open access, thereby maximizing its re-use.

3.1 Findable (meta) data

3.1.1 Data discoverability and identification mechanisms

Enhancing the discoverability of the data gathered/generated during the course of Flex4Res' activities is a priority. To achieve this, the project adopts a metadata-driven methodology to improve the data's searchability while facilitating its comprehension and re-use. "Data about data" or "information about

information" is what metadata is defined as. A digital resource, whether it be a single file, a portion of a single file, or a collection of many files, usually contains structured textual information that describes something about its conception, content, or context. The World Wide Web's information and data are connected by metadata. It is a tool that facilitates the discovery, management, description, preservation, and development of connections among digital resources.

In particular, three distinct types of metadata exist, as presented below:

- ❖ **Descriptive metadata**, collections and related information resources using descriptive metadata. Local descriptive metadata facilitates searching and retrieval. Descriptive metadata aids resource discovery in an online setting. Usually contains details like the title, author, date, description, identifier, etc.
- ❖ **Administrative metadata** is employed to simplify the administration of information assets. Both short- and long-term management and processing of data can benefit from it. Typically, the public will not be interested in this information, but staff members will need it to manage collections on an internal level. These metadata could include things like acquisition and location data.
- ❖ **Structural metadata**, the navigation and presentation of electronic resources are made possible by structural metadata. It explains the hierarchy of a product's parts. A manuscript or scrapbook, the arrangement of pages to create chapters, or the JPEG and TIF files made from the original photograph negative and linked together are examples of structural metadata.

In light of this, Flex4Res data is discoverable with metadata appropriate to its content and format. To achieve this, the project uses metadata standards to generate rich and consistent metadata to support long-term discovery, use, and integrity (further information on the metadata standards used by Flex4Res can be found in Subsection 3.1.5).

The data generated by Flex4Res and accepted for sharing and re-use will also be deposited to Zenodo (www.zenodo.org), an open data repository, in order to further improve data discoverability. The open data for the project will be made freely accessible through the use of this data repository, which was developed by OpenAIRE (<https://www.openaire.eu/>) and CERN (<https://home.cern/>). In fact, Zenodo creates and runs a straightforward service that allows, among others, researchers, scientists, EU projects, and institutions to share and showcase research outcomes (including data and publications) that are not included in the current institutional or subject-based repositories of the research communities. It supports peer-reviewed, publicly accessible research, allows users to create their own collections, accepts any file format, and is freely accessible for Flex4Res to upload and share data as well as other stakeholders to explore, download, and reuse this data.

A standard identification mechanism can be used to locate the data generated during project implementation thanks to the use of this data repository. In fact, Flex4Res will be able to give Persistent Identifiers (PIDs) to any data that is uploaded to Zenodo that are globally resolvable. A dataset is given an identifier, which is a special identification code, so that it can be referenced clearly. For instance, a catalogue number identifies a specific specimen, and an ISBN code identifies a specific book. PIDs are persistent identifiers that make it possible to refer to a digital object indefinitely. In other words, PIDs assign a distinctive and permanent reference number to digital resources like documents, images, and data records.

Additionally, in its capacity as a digital repository, Zenodo registers Digital Object Identifiers (DOIs) for all submitted data through DataCite (<https://www.datacite.org/>), the foremost international nonprofit that offers PIDs (and specifically DOIs for research data), and preserves these submissions using the secure and reliable foundation of CERN's data center, along with the largest scientific dataset in the world, the LHC's 100PB Big Data store. As a result, the DOIs (<http://dx.doi.org/>) will serve as everlasting

links to the resources, and the data preserved in Zenodo will remain searchable for years. Due to resolvers (like DOI), DOIs are still valuable because they are resistant to changes in Uniform Resource Locator (URL) or protocol.

The project's web portal will serve as a searchable repository for datasets not uploaded to Zenodo at the same time. These datasets will make use of well-tailored identification mechanisms, such as standard naming conventions, to ensure their consistency and make them simple to find for project partners. More information on this is provided in the subsection that follows.

3.1.2 Naming conventions

When creating the project's data files, using a standardized set of naming conventions can greatly improve their searchability. In order to increase their discoverability, Flex4Res generates consistent data file names that offer hints as to their content, status, and versioning. By doing this, project participants and other interested parties can categorize and sort files with ease. A best practice for naming conventions, according to the UK Data Archive (UK Data Service, 2017b), is to give data files succinct but meaningful names that make classification easier.

Spaces, dots, and other special characters (like & or!) should not be used in file names, and the use of underscores to clearly delineate the parts of the file name is recommended. Versioning should also be incorporated into naming conventions to make it clear what changes and edits have been made to a file. Flex4Res uses a standard naming convention that incorporates versioning and accounts for the potential for creating multiple datasets during an activity that involves data collection or generation with this in mind and to make it easier to refer to the datasets that will be produced during its implementation. This problem is taken into account in Flex4Res' naming convention, which is solved by using a special element that counts the number of datasets generated by a single activity. The project's naming structure is described in more detail below.

Flex4Res_ [Name of Study] _ [Number of dataset] _ [Issue Date] _ [Version number]

- ❖ Flex4Res: The name of the project.
- ❖ Name of Study: a condensed form of the activity's full name, for which the dataset is being created.
- ❖ Number of datasets: an indication of the dataset's assigned number.
- ❖ Issue Date: The date on which the latest version of the dataset was modified (YYYY.MM.DD.).
- ❖ Version number: the dataset's versioning number.

3.1.3 Search keywords

Search keywords will be added to the project's data to maximize how interested parties can use it throughout its entire lifespan. In light of this, the Flex4Res metadata standards offer opportunities for keyword tagging the data collected/generated and its content. Typically, words and phrases used to name data are included in keywords, which are a subset of metadata. Keywords are used in the context of Flex4Res to enrich the data generated/collected with useful information and to make it easier to describe and interpret its value.

Along these lines, the following tenets serve as the foundation for the project's keyword strategy:

- ❖ The who, what, when, where, and why should all be explained.
- ❖ Ensure that the various keyword tags are consistent with one another.
- ❖ Keywording that is pertinent, understandable, and clear should be sought after.

The quadruple helix, open innovation, co-creation, and SMEs will typically be included as keywords. The keywords will accurately reflect the datasets' content and steer clear of phrases that appear just once or twice in them.

3.1.4 Versioning

Versioning information enables a revision of datasets to be uniquely identified and can be used to identify which version the creators or editors are currently working with as well as whether and how data changed over time. Furthermore, by implementing effective data versioning, it is possible to find out if a newer dataset version is available and to pinpoint the differences between versions. This capability makes comparisons possible, eliminates ambiguity, and improves comprehension of the dataset's evolution. Every data file created during the course of Flex4Res is named in this context with an explicit version number indicator to make it easier to distinguish between different versions.

3.1.5 Standards for metadata creation

Flex4Res employs standards for creating metadata for the data collected/generated by the project, to describe it with rich metadata and thus improve their discoverability and searchability. Effective searching, enhanced digital curation, and simple sharing will result as a result. The applied metadata standards also make it possible to incorporate metadata from various sources into other technical systems.

In light of this, **Zenodo's metadata standards will be applied to Flex4Res's publicly accessible data**. To make the datasets accessible to a wider range of interested stakeholders, Zenodo creates metadata to go along with them when they are uploaded to its repository. Following the recommendations of OpenAIRE, this metadata can be exported in a variety of formats, including open and machine-readable ones (like MARCXML, Dublin Core, and DataCite Metadata Schema), and is stored by Zenodo in JSON format in accordance with a specified JSON schema¹.

Data from the project that cannot be reused will also have open, machine-readable metadata added to it in accordance with the Dublin Core Metadata standard. One of the most well-known metadata standards that is simple to comprehend and apply is the Dublin Core Metadata Element Set (certified with the ISO Standard 15836). It was initially created as a fundamental set of components for cataloging web page content and facilitating search and retrieval. One of the factors that led to the choice of this standard is that Zenodo is compatible with Dublin Core metadata formats, ensuring that any data that is initially closed but later becomes open (for instance, as a result of a change in the consortium's policy) will retain its metadata.

The Dublin Core metadata standard is a straightforward yet efficient framework for developing rich metadata that will describe a variety of resources. The [Dublin Core Metadata Initiative \(DCMI\)](#) maintains a larger collection of metadata vocabularies and technical specifications, which includes the fifteen-element "Dublin Core" that is described in this standard. Additionally, sets of resource classes, vocabulary encoding schemes, and syntax encoding schemes are included in the complete set of vocabularies. The various metadata components will be created using a web-based metadata generator ([dublincoregenerator.com](#)).

3.2 Making data openly accessible

3.2.1 Openly available and closed data

To ensure that data subjects cannot be identified in any reports, publications, and/or datasets produced by the project, **only anonymized and aggregated data will be made available**. The project partner acting as **the data controller in each instance will carry out all required anonymization** steps to de-identify the data subject and make it anonymous (further information on data management responsibilities is provided in Section 4.2).

To this end, it is crucial to keep in mind that data identifiers must be eliminated, generalized, aggregated, or distorted during the data anonymization process. In addition, anonymization differs from pseudonymization, which is classified under a separate heading in the GDPR; anonymization theoretically eliminates all means of re-identifying the data subject, whereas pseudonymization permits re-identification with additional information. Accordingly, the list of best practices for anonymizing quantitative and qualitative data in the table below is taken from the Consortium of European Social Science Data Archives' (CESSDA) tour guide on data management.

Table 4. Data anonymization best practices

Type Of Data	Good Practices
Quantitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ <i>Deleting or aggregating variables, lowering their precision, or reducing their textual meaning.</i> ❖ <i>Increase or decrease a variable's precision, such as age or residence. Report the least amount of georeferencing that could possibly compromise respondent confidentiality.</i> ❖ <i>By substituting more general text for potentially disclosed free-text responses, you can generalize the meaning of a detailed text variable.</i> <p>If values for some people are outliers or atypical within the larger group under study, limit a continuous variable's upper or lower ranges to hide them.</p>
Qualitative data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ❖ <i>Edit identifying information using pseudonyms or general descriptors rather than by leaving it blank;</i> ❖ <i>Plan to anonymize data when transcribing or writing up the initial write-up (longitudinal studies may be an exception if relationships between waves of interviews require special consideration for harmonised editing).</i> ❖ <i>Use consistent pseudonyms or replacements throughout the project and within the research team. Using the same aliases in publications and subsequent research, for instance;</i> ❖ <i>Be careful when using 'search and replace' techniques to avoid making unintended changes and missing misspelled words;</i> ❖ <i>Identify replacements in text clearly, for example with [brackets] or using XML tags such as <seg>word to be anonymised</seg>;</i> <p><i>All replacements, aggregations, and removals should be recorded in an anonymization log (also referred to as a de-anonymization key), which should be kept secure and apart from the anonymized data files.</i></p>

Source: Tour guide on data management of the CESSDA²

In light of this, the data that was gathered or created during the project and will be made publicly available is shown in the following table. An explanation should be given if certain data cannot be shared or must only be shared under certain conditions.

Table 5. Data Availability

No	Data	Availability	Notes
1	Analysis of the needs and requirements of	Open	-

¹ For more information on the JSON format and the JSON schema visit the following website: <http://json-schema.org/>

² Retrieved from: <https://www.cessda.eu/Research-Infrastructure/Training/Expert-Tour-Guide-on-Data-Management/5.-Protect/Anonymisation>

	prospective users and stakeholders.		
2	Monitoring, evaluation and validation of Flex4Res's pilots	Open	-
3	Monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication results	Open	-
4	Web portal analytics	Open	-
5	Social media statistics	Open	-
6	Project events data	Closed	This data will remain closed (accessible only to consortium members) as it is useful only for internal reporting purposes. On top of that, any anonymization will leave no data within the dataset.
7	Newsletter subscriptions	Closed	This data will remain closed (accessible only to consortium members) as it is useful only for internal reporting purposes. On top of that, any anonymization will leave no data within the dataset.

To protect the privacy of the data subjects, it is important to note that all personal data generated or collected will be regarded as closed data before being anonymized and compiled.

The consortium partners who collected the data will securely store it so that it can only be kept in their records for as long as is required to fulfill their contractual obligations to Flex4Res's funding authority, the Research Executive Agency (REA) of the Commission, and no longer than five years after the project has ended. Only those employees of the consortium partner who collected the personal data for Flex4Res and the REA will have access to it during this time. The personal information will be removed from the respective consortium partner's files after this time frame.

3.2.2 Data accessibility and availability

Through Zenodo, which will automatically link to OpenAIRE, the public will have access to the open data. Because of the included metadata and Zenodo's search functionality, the data will be completely accessible. At the same time, closed data will be kept and distributed among authorized consortium members via the project's web portal. In light of this, the following table outlines the locations in the context of Flex4Res where data will be made available.

Table 6. Data Accessibility

No	Data	Accessibility
1	Analysis of the needs and requirements of prospective users and stakeholders.	Open Repositories

2	Monitoring, evaluation and validation of Flex4Res's pilots	<i>Open Repositories</i>
3	Monitoring and assessment of the dissemination and communication results	<i>Open Repositories</i>
4	Web portal analytics	<i>Open Repositories</i>
5	Social media statistics	<i>Open Repositories</i>
6	Project events data	-
7	Newsletter subscriptions	-

3.2.3 Methods, software tools and documentation to access the data

Closed data can be accessed only by authorised project partners through the Flex4Res Microsoft Teams group. Access to the group can be requested from the coordinator of the project (LMS).

3.2.4 Restrictions

Flex4Res's can apply different levels of accessibility for this data while taking into account any pertinent issues (such as ethical, rules of personal data, intellectual property, commercial, privacy-related, security-related, etc.) by using Zenodo to share the project's openly available data.

3.2.5 BCI Data (Business contact information)

BCI data will be kept on file for as long as the Grant Agreement is in effect, after it expires for as long as it is required to do so in order to defend against legal claims, and then for however long is necessary to keep the data on file in order to comply with a more specific legal framework, such as tax law.

3.2.6 Data Protection

Specific responsibilities regarding data protection

Within the framework of the performance and management of the Project and of this Consortium Agreement, the Parties shall cooperate as necessary to enable one another to fulfill legal obligations arising under applicable data protection legislation and applicable national data protection laws applicable to said Party. In particular, before any data processing or sharing occurs, the Parties shall, as necessary, reach a separate data processing, data sharing, and/or joint controller agreement.

Exchange of Business Contact Information:

In the context of this Agreement, whenever either Party Processes the personnel BCI of the other Party, the processing shall be done by each Party in the capacity of a Data Controller for its own business contact information, and shall only be done for administrative management purposes. As a result, each Party commits to abiding by the relevant data protection laws.

Other Personal Data:

The Parties affirm that they may be required to share background information, results, confidential information, and/or other data and/or information ("Shared Information") with one another in order to carry out the Action and/or for any Exploitation activities. Regarding the Shared Information, each Party agrees to abide by the Applicable Data Protection Legislation.

The open access level will be primarily used by project partners to share project data with interested parties. However, as explained in Subsection 3.2.1, embargo periods or access restrictions may occasionally be used. Only authorized members of the Flex4Res consortium and/or authorized staff from the REA of the Commission will have access to data that cannot be reused.

Additionally, Flex4Res will guarantee open access to any peer-reviewed academic publications that might be created throughout the course of the project. Flex4Res will, in particular, comply with the Grant Agreement's:

- ❖ Deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication as soon as possible and no later than on publication in a repository for scientific publications. Additionally, deposit the research data required to verify the findings presented in the deposited scientific publications at the same time.
- ❖ Make sure there is free, open access to the deposited publication through the repository as soon as it is published, or within six months if there is a free electronic version available from the publisher.
- ❖ Preserve open access to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the deposited publication via the repository. The terms "European Union (EU)" and "HORIZON Innovation Actions" as well as the acronym and grant number for the action, the publication date, the length of the embargo period, if any, and a PID must all be included in the bibliographic metadata.

In order to make the data in the Flex4Res framework as openly accessible as possible to any stakeholder who might find it useful for reusing, this section has provided the methodology used there. To improve its data interoperability in this context, Flex4Res also focuses on offering metadata standards and suitable metadata vocabularies. More information on this is provided in the section that follows.

3.3 Making data interoperable

Data interoperability is the capacity of systems and services to have clear, shared expectations for the contents, context, and meaning of that data³ in their creation, exchange, and use. In light of this, Flex4Res has incorporated metadata vocabularies, standards, and techniques into its data management methodology to improve the interoperability of the data generated by and collected through its operations. More specifically, implementing the Dublin Core Metadata standard will make it easier for the data that won't be shared publicly to interoperate.

This specification is a condensed "metadata element set" that takes into account the problems that need to be fixed in order to guarantee that data adhere to established norms for consistency and quality while remaining largely interoperable with other data sources in the linked data environment. The standard's fifteen components offer a vocabulary of terms with natural-language definitions, such as title, creator, and author, which are instantly converted into open machine-readable formats, like XML and HTML, to enable machine-processability. The standard itself provides ways to improve each element and encourages the use of encoding and vocabulary schemes. Each element is optional and may be repeated. The Dublin Core Metadata standard's⁴ vocabulary is shown in the following table:

Table 7. Dublin Core Metadata Standard Vocabulary

No	Element	Element Definition
1	Title	A name given to the resource.
2	Creator	An entity primarily responsible for making the content of the resource.

³L. Steele & T. Orrell (2017). The frontiers of data interoperability for sustainable development. Publish What You Fund and Development Initiatives

⁴Sugimoto, S., Baker, T., & Weibel, S. L. (2002). Dublin Core: Process and Principles. Lecture Notes in Computer Science Digital Libraries: People, Knowledge, and Technology, 25-35.

3	Subject	The topic of the content of the resource.
4	Description	An account of the content of the resource.
5	Publisher	An entity responsible for making the resource available.
6	Contributor	An entity responsible for making contributions to the content of the resource.
7	Date	A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource
8	Type	The nature or genre of the content of the resource.
9	Format	The physical or digital manifestation of the resource.
10	Identifier	An unambiguous reference to the resource within a given context.
11	Source	A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived.

In a similar vein, Zenodo will aid in the interoperability of publicly accessible data because its metadata will be internally stored in JSON format in accordance with a predefined JSON schema. This contains HTML microdata, which enables the nested groups of name-value pairs to contain machine-readable data in HTML documents. Additionally, the JSON schema offers a set of microdata-formatted shared vocabularies that can be used to mark up pages in a way that the major search engines can comprehend. Furthermore, the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) allows for the export of all metadata associated with the open data, allowing for its harvesting. The OAI-PMH creates and supports standards for interoperability that enable effective data dissemination among various communities⁵.

3.4 Mechanisms to increase re-use

This section will outline the methods for piquing a third party's interest and encouraging data reuse.

3.4.1 License schemes to permit the widest use possible

The open data provided by Flex4Res can easily be made available for reuse by any interested third party by adding a license to it. In this context, licenses are the means by which a third party is given permission to copy, distribute, display, and/or modify project data, but only for the purposes specified by the license. Permissions are typically granted under the condition that certain criteria are met by licenses. While specifics vary, three requirements—*attribution, non-derivative, and non-commerciality*—are frequently found in licenses.

Accordingly, Flex4Res publishes its freely accessible data under the **Creative Commons licensing scheme** to encourage re-use and create an environment that is fair and open to all. In fact, Zenodo gives Flex4Res the option to share its open data under the following five **Creative Common licenses**:

- ❖ Any third party may freely copy, distribute, display, and modify the datasets for any purpose under the terms of the **Creative Commons Attribution-Share Alike 4.0 (CC BY-SA 4.0) license**. Data that has been remixed, transformed, or built upon must be released under the same license as the original. Third parties are required to give due credit, include a link to the license, and state whether any modifications were made.

Figure 1 CC BY-SA 4.0

⁵See [here](#), Corrado, E.M. (2005) 'The importance of open access, open source, and open standards for libraries', *Issues in Science and Technology Librarianship*.

- ❖ The datasets are available for free copying, distribution, display, and modification for any purpose under the terms of the **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)**. It is required for third parties to give due credit, include a link to the license, and state whether any changes were made.

Figure 2 CC BY 4.0

- ❖ **Creative Commons Attribution-No Derivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-ND 4.0)**, which entitles any third party to unrestricted use of the datasets for any purpose, including unrestricted copying, distribution, display, and modification. Data that has been transformed, remixed, or built upon cannot be distributed. Third parties are required to give due credit, include a link to the license, and state whether any modifications were made.

Figure 3 CC BY-ND 4.0

- ❖ Unless they first obtain permission from the project partners, third parties are permitted to copy, distribute, display, and modify the datasets under the terms of the **Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International (CC BY-NC 4.0)**. Third parties are required to give due credit, include a link to the license, and state whether any modifications were made.

Figure 4 CC BY-NC 4.0

- ❖ Unless they first obtain permission from the project partners, third parties are permitted to copy, distribute, display, and modify the datasets under the terms of the **Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivatives 4.0 International (CC BY-NC-ND 4.0)**. Data that has been transformed, remixed, or built upon cannot be distributed. Third parties are required to give due credit, include a link to the license, and state whether any modifications were made.

Figure 5 CC BY-NC-ND 4.0

With this in mind, the Flex4Res consortium believes that the CC BY-NC 4.0 is an appropriate licensing scheme to ensure the data's most widespread re-use while also taking into account how important it is to acknowledge the data's source and authority as well as to protect the project platform's financial interests.

However, different licensing models might be better suited to the requirements of Flex4Res' open data, ensuring not only their long-term preservation and re-use but also the interests of the consortium and the rights of the people the data is about in addition to those of the consortium.

3.4.2 Availability for re-use

A crucial part of Flex4Res' methodology for making data FAIR is the reuse of data. In fact, allowing data to be reused ensures that interested parties, including other project partners, can profit from this data, helping to maximize the project's impact. The re-use of **Flex4Res' open data is facilitated by rich metadata** built on metadata standards that allow proper discovery as well as **appropriate licensing schemes**, allowing them to find useful applications.

To ensure that any additional data management activities necessary to this end do not compete with the timely delivery of the project's planned outputs, it is expected that data will become available for re-use no later than 120 days after the end of its processing in the context of the project (i.e., collection, anonymization, aggregation, etc.).

3.4.3 Data quality assurance processes

Prior to publishing any data to Zenodo, Flex4Res implements **quality assurance (QA)** and **quality control (QC)** activities as part of its data management methodology to ensure the data's transparency, consistency, comparability, completeness, and accuracy.

QA is a planned system of review procedures carried out by personnel not directly involved in the dataset development process, outside the context of developing a dataset^{6,7}. It takes the form of **peer reviews of methods and/or data summaries** in the context of Flex4Res to evaluate the dataset's quality and identify any areas in need of improvement, ensuring that the dataset accurately incorporates the generated scientific knowledge and data.

QC is a system of checks to evaluate and uphold the consistency and quality of the compiled dataset^{7,8}. As they measure and control data consistency, integrity, correctness, and completeness as well as identify and correct errors and omissions, the relevant Flex4Res procedures are created to provide routine technical checks. The application of approved procedures and methods, documentation, and data acquisition and handling are all included in this context's QC checks. Checking for transcription errors in data input, ensuring scale measures are within the range of acceptable values, and determining whether proper naming conventions are used are just a few of the general quality checks carried out as part of the project.

4 Allocation of resources

4.1 Estimated costs

The project budget includes the expenses necessary to make the data generated during Flex4Res's activities FAIR. These projected costs will be required to pay for a number of particular data management and processing activities:

- ❖ Collection
- ❖ Documentation
- ❖ Storage
- ❖ Access And Security
- ❖ Preservation
- ❖ Availability and Re-use
- ❖ Overall Data Management

The required effort will be included in the relevant WP since these activities are a part of the WP under which the relevant data are processed. WP1 includes the overall data management plan activity.

Since most of Flex4Res's data is new data collected or generated throughout the project, the majority of the costs associated with making data FAIR are reflected in the data processing done during the collection activity. In addition, data documentation costs cover the time spent on describing data (such as labeling data with variable and value descriptions, code descriptions, etc.), creating well-defined metadata, and (if necessary) providing a detailed explanation of the context and methodology of data collection, generation, and processing.

⁶Corrado, E.M. (2005) 'The importance of open access, open source, and open standards for libraries', Issues in Science and Technology Librarianship.

⁷2006 IPCC Guidelines for National Greenhouse Gas Inventories, Vol. 1 General Guidance and Reporting, CHAPTER

⁸Quality Assurance / Quality Control and Verification.

Data storage expenses cover both the resources needed to guarantee enough storage space for the data as well as the time spent performing data backups. On the other hand, costs associated with ensuring access to the data as well as safeguarding it from unauthorized access, use, or disclosure are included in data access and security costs. Such costs are kept to a minimum because storing Flex4Res's data won't require purchasing extra space (in addition to what project partners already have access to), and because no special tools or software are needed to access and secure the data (aside from what is already included in the repositories of Flex4Res's data).

The costs associated with data preservation, on the other hand, are anticipated to be somewhat higher than those associated with data storage, access, and security, as more work will frequently be needed to transform the collected or generated data from its original form (such as physical interview transcripts) into an open and/or machine-readable format suitable for long-term preservation (such as an.xlsx format). The proper digitization and anonymization of the data, as well as any resources needed for data sharing and cleaning, are all safeguarded by adequate effort for data availability and re-use costs. To cover the effort related to the operationalization of data management within the Flex4Res framework, an appropriate effort is also anticipated for overall data management.

The fees that some scientific journal publishers demand in order to provide open access to articles or journals are another potential expense. The price to publish a hybrid journal of the IEEE, for instance, can be \$1750⁷. Costs vary depending on the journal and publisher. In the context of Flex4Res, costs for long-term preservation are anticipated to be minimal because the project's open data will be hosted in a free environment.

4.2 Data management responsibilities

For the effective, proper and secure handling of the data collected/generated in the framework of Flex4Res, specific data management roles have been established within the data management methodology and procedures of the project. These responsibilities are outlined in this section of the DMP and are as follows.

Project Coordinator (PC): The PC, LMS, is in charge of directing the execution of Flex4Res' data processing activities, including developing the DMP and any updates (as needed and with the assistance of all partners). The PC is also in charge of creating appropriate templates for the informed consent form and information sheet so that they can be properly modified and used by project partners during the pertinent project activities. To determine whether and how the data gathered/generated by Flex4Res are shared and made available for reuse, the PC coordinates with Work Package and Task Leaders.

Work Package Leader (WPL): The WPL is in charge of organizing the execution of the data processing tasks carried out within the WPs they are leading. Additionally, they agree with the PC and the relevant Work Task Leader on the sharing and/or reuse of the data produced under the tasks that fall under the WP they are leading. This includes any necessary software and/or other tools that may be necessary for data sharing and re-use, as well as the definition of access procedures, potential embargo periods, and access procedures themselves. Last but not least, the WPL is the main person in charge of ensuring the quality of the data resulting from the WP activities they are leading, including evaluating their quality and alerting the relevant Work Task Leaders to any areas that need improvement.

Work Task Leaders (WTL): The WTL act as data controllers for the data generated or collected as part of the tasks they oversee, choosing the methods and purposes for processing it and ensuring that it is used properly and promptly. Additionally, it is their responsibility to properly adapt the templates for the informed consent form and information sheet to the requirements and particulars of the tasks they are

⁹<https://open.ieee.org/index.php/about-ieee-open-access/faqs/>

leading. Finally, they take whatever steps are required to get the data gathered or generated by the tasks they are leading ready for sharing, either within the consortium or publicly (such as using proper naming conventions, applying appropriate anonymization techniques, creating the necessary metadata and documentation, etc.).

Data processors: Project partners known as data processors are tasked with gathering, digitizing, anonymizing, storing, destroying, and/or otherwise processing data for the particular activity for which it was generated or collected as part of the project. They are in charge of properly obtaining the consent required for data processing and making sure that the informed consent form and information sheet used to that end are properly tailored to the requirements of the activity they are taking part in and any unique circumstances that may be relevant to their organization. Additionally, they are in charge of managing the consents they have obtained in order to prove their adherence to the pertinent national and EU regulations. In order to evaluate and maintain the quality of the dataset(s) contained within their records, they perform quality checks.

Data repositories: The storage and long-term preservation of the project's data is the responsibility of data repositories. In this way, task repositories preserve and maintain Flex4Res' publicly accessible data, allowing for its sharing and reuse. To ensure its long-term preservation, data repositories assign metadata and DOIs to the data while also taking all necessary precautions to securely back-up the data and be in a position to restore it. As a result, the Flex4Res Web Portal shall securely store and preserve the project's data so that it may be shared within the project's framework by authorized consortium members. In this context, the following table demonstrates how the Flex4Res consortium's members were assigned data management duties based on the data generated or collected under each WP.

Table 8. Data Management Responsibilities of Flex4Res partners under each WP

WP	WPL	Tasks	WTL Data Controllers	Data Processors
WP1	IDE	T1.1	IDE	All partners
		T1.2	IFT	LMS, VOE, SID, GOI, SOR, INTR, CONTACT, BEIA, SAV, PTW, USI, IDE
		T1.3	INTRA	LMS, VOE, SID, HANS, SOR, CONT, A1, BEIA, SAV, MON, IFT, PTW, USI, IDE
WP2	INTRA	T2.1	INTRA	LMS, HANS, GOI, SOR, CONT, A1, SAV, MON, IFT, PTW, USI, IDE
		T2.2	CONT	LMS, VOE, SID, GOI, SOR, INTR, SAV, MON, PTW, IDE
		T2.3	A1	LMS, INTR, CONT, BEIA, SAV, IFT, PTW, IDE, USI
WP3	LMS	T3.1	PTW	LMS, VOE, CONT, SAV, MON, IFT, USI, IDE
		T3.2	LMS	VOE, SID, GOI, SOR, INTR, SAV, PTW, IDE
		T3.3	IFT	VOE, HANS, GOI, SOR, CONT, SAV, PTW, USI, IDE
WP4	USI	T4.1	USI	HANS, GOI, SOR, CONT, BEIA, SAV, IFT, PTW, IDE
		T4.2	LMS	VOE, SID, INTR, CONT, PTW
		T4.3	IFT	VOE, HANS, GOI, CONT, SAV, PTW, USI, IDE
WP5	PTW	T5.1	PTW	LMS, VOE, SID, HANS, GOI, SOR, EITM, INTR, CONT, A1, SAV, IFT, USI, IDE

		T5.2	VOE	CONT, IFT, PTW
		T5.3	SID	LMS, INTR
		T5.4	HANS	BEIA, IFT, USI
		T5.5	GOI	SOR, SAV, MON, IDE
WP6	EITM	T6.1	EITM	All partners
		T6.2	EITM	LMS, VOE, SID, GOI, SOR, INTR, CONT, A1, BEIA, SAV, IFT, PTW, USI, IDE
		T6.3	MON	LMS, VOE, HANS, EITM, INTR, CONT, A1, BEIA, SAV, IFT, PTW, IDE
WP7	LMS	T7.1	LMS	VOE, SID, HANS, GOI, SOR, EITM, INTR, A1, BEIA, SAV, IFT, PTW, USI, IDE

5 Conclusion

This deliverable aims to describe the data management plan that will be followed within Flex4Res project in order to safeguard the sound management of data collected during the project. There is the need for creating FAIR data, ensuring security of sensitive information and addressing ethical aspects regarding the collection or generation of the data.

The Data Management Plan will be seamlessly updated throughout the course of Flex4Res project in order to accumulate the latest development needs and available results. In each periodic project management report, the proposed plan will be reviewed in order to ensure that all data-related aspects are covered within this document and that there is a valid plan for maintaining and securing that information. The goal is that information aggregated during this research project and helped the developments will be re-used in future research while also protecting the industrial partners sensitive information.

Annex

Privacy policy of Flex4Res portal

Introduction

Thank you for visiting our website, which has been developed and now runs in the frame of the H2020 “DATA SPACES FOR FLEXIBLE PRODUCTION LINES AND SUPPLY CHAINS FOR RESILIENT MANUFACTURING”, or “Flex4Res” for short.

Flex4Res is being implemented by a consortium led by the [Laboratory for Manufacturing Systems \(LMS\), Greece](#) while the website of Flex4Res is being managed by [EIT MANUFACTURING CENTRAL, Germany](#). More information about the consortium of Flex4Res can be found [here](#).

In this context, your privacy is important for us, and we are committed to protect it in accordance with the European General Data Protection Regulation 679/2016 (GDPR). To this end, we provide this Privacy Policy that applies to the Flex4Res website and governs personal information collection and usage by the website only.

By using this website, you consent to the personal information practices described in this Privacy Policy which is effective from 01/01/2023. We reserve the right to update or change our Privacy Policy at any time. With that in mind, you should periodically check this Privacy Policy.

Type of personal information that we collect

While using our website, you may share with us, on a voluntary basis, your e-mail address, name, country, region, and company (optional) through the contact page of the Flex4Res website and/or by subscribing to our newsletter.

Use of personal information that we collect

We may use this information to contact you with newsletters, to disseminate information about Flex4Res’ activities and results or to promote information from other projects or third parties which we think you may find interesting. We will not use this information for any purpose other than those described in this Privacy Policy without informing and /or obtaining your consent first, when necessary.

Sharing of personal information that we collect

The website of Flex4Res does not sell or lease its contact list to third parties. The Flex4Res website keeps a copy of its contact list to email server, which is used only for e-mail campaigns and newsletters distribution.

The personal information collected through the Flex4Res website may be shared within the consortium of Flex4Res to contact you for specific dissemination purposes. All such third parties are prohibited from using your personal information except to provide dissemination to Flex4Res, and they are required to maintain the confidentiality of your information, according to Flex4Res’ privacy policy. The website of Flex4Res will disclose your personal information, without notice, only if required to do so by law.

Storage and deletion of personal information that we collect

Any personal information you are provide us through the Flex4Res website is securely stored by the [Laboratory for Manufacturing Systems \(LMS\), Greece](#) only for as long as necessary for us to comply with our contractual obligations to the funding authority of Flex4Res, namely the Research Executive Agency (REA) of the European Commission, and no longer than 5 years from Flex4Res’ completion. You can unsubscribe from our contact list and/or request for your personal information to be deleted anytime by opting to unsubscribe in the e-mails and/or newsletters that you receive from us, or by directly [contacting us](#) (e-mail: flex4res@lms.mech.upatras.gr).

Security of personal information that we collect

Flex4Res' website takes information security seriously and uses reasonable physical, electronic, and managerial procedures to help prevent unauthorized access, maintain data security, and correctly use the information we collect.

Your rights

You have a number of rights, which you can exercise at any time. In particular, you have the:

- ❖ Right to be informed: You have the right to be informed about the collection and use of your personal information, including the purpose for which we are processing this information, the period that we will retain it and with whom we will share it.
- ❖ Right of access: You have the right to ask from us to confirm whether or not we are processing personal information concerning you. Where that is the case, you can access your personal information that we are processing and relevant supplementary information.
- ❖ Right to rectification: You have the right to request from us modifications to your personal information in case you believe that it is not up to date, complete or accurate.
- ❖ Right to erasure ("right to be forgotten"): You have the right to ask us to erase your personal information that we are processing.
- ❖ Right to restrict processing: You have the right to request from us to restrict the processing of your personal information, with a view to limiting the way that we use this information.
- ❖ Right to data portability: You have the right to ask for your personal information to be provided back to you or transferred to a third party.
- ❖ Right to object: You have the right to object to us processing your personal information at any time for reasons related to your particular situation.
- ❖ Right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing (including profiling), which produces legal effects concerning you or similarly significantly affects you.

To exercise your rights, send us a notice to flex4res@lms.mech.upatras.gr. Please keep in mind that you also have the right to lodge a complaint a supervisory authority (e.g., the Data Protection Authority within your region or country), should you wish so.

Third-Party Websites

Our website may contain links to or the ability for you to access third-party websites. We are not responsible for the privacy practices employed by those third parties, nor are we responsible for the information or content their websites contain. This Privacy Policy applies solely to information collected by us. We encourage you to read the privacy policies of any third parties before proceeding to use their websites.

Children

We do not knowingly collect, use, or disclose information from children under 16. If we learn that we have collected the personal information of a child under 16 we will take steps to delete the information as soon as possible. Please immediately [contact us](#) if you become aware that a child under 16 has provided us with personal information.

Cookies

Cookies are small text files which are saved on your computer, mobile phone or tablet. They allow the website to remember your actions and preferences (such as login, language, font size and other display preferences) so you don't have to keep re-entering them whenever you come back to the site.

You can control and/or delete cookies as you wish. If you do this, however, you may need to manually adjust your preferences every time you visit a website. For more information on how to manage cookies, please visit: <http://www.aboutcookies.org/>

Google analytics

We use tools like Google Analytics to better understand how visitors interact with our website. This provides us with important information to enable the site to work better. The information collected is not linked to your personal data.

For more information on the cookies set by Google Analytics, please visit: <http://code.google.com/apis/analytics/docs/concepts/gaConceptsCookies.html>

If you do not wish your information to be sent to Google Analytics, you can install the Google Analytics Opt-out Browser Add-on.

Contact us

If you have any questions about this Privacy Policy, please contact us, or send us an e-mail at: media@flex4resproject.eu or flex4res@lms.mech.upatras.gr